

Research Proposal: Exploring Mind-Body Therapies for Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder in Autistic Women and Gender-Diverse Individuals

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ABSTRACT:

Autistic people may be more likely to experience trauma, cumulative trauma and PTSD. This mixed methods research proposal aims to address significant gaps in autism and trauma research. Autistic women and gender-diverse individuals face significant barriers in autism research. Existing diagnostic and treatment models are based on male-centric frameworks, leading to underdiagnosis, misdiagnosis, and inadequate support for this population. While validated trauma interventions for autistic people are scarce in general, autistic women and gender-diverse individuals are almost absent in these studies. To address these gaps, this thesis has 4 main sections; 1) a literature review on existing research, 2) a survey on expert perspectives in this context, 3) A scoping review on methodologies for mind-body treatments in this population, 4) proposed randomised controlled trials on mind-body therapies for this population and 4b) proposed interviews evaluating the lived experience of this population before, during and after the trials. The integration of expert knowledge, quantitative outcomes and lived experience in this research challenges gender biases in autism care and adds to the development of autism-informed trauma treatments. Findings of this thesis and the proposed trials may provide critical insight into trauma-informed care for autistic women and gender-diverse individuals, influencing both practice and policy.

Keywords: Autism, PTSD, gender disparities, mind-body therapy, mixed-methods research

INTRODUCTION:

This project has multiple aims; 1) To identify expert perspectives on autistic women and gender-diverse people with trauma; 2) To look into the lived experience of autistic women and gender-diverse people with PTSD, focusing on their experience of mind-body therapy; 3) To research the efficacy and methodology of mind-body therapies for autistic women and gender-diverse people with PTSD.

The research question and sub-questions are as follows; What are the key differences and themes in the lived experiences of autistic women and gender-diverse individuals with PTSD compared to non-autistic women/autistic men with PTSD? How do experts perceive and approach trauma screening and treatment for autistic women and gender-diverse individuals? How effective are mind-body therapies in addressing the specific challenges faced by autistic women and gender-diverse individuals with PTSD?

This evidence backed research proposal uses a mixed methods approach, allowing a scoping literature review, expert perspectives and semi-structured interviews with autistic women to inform and enrich the proposed randomised controlled trials. There are therefore multiple parts to the final proposal; 1) A literature review outlining the knowledge, gaps, relevance, need for research on autistic women and gender-diverse people with PTSD; 2) A pilot study using an semi-structured survey for experts, which will be thematically analysed; 3) A scoping literature review on the methodologies used in mind-body treatments for ASD populations; 4) The final study proposal including the methodology for the semi-structured interviews and the randomised controlled mind-body therapy trials.

This project is crucial in addressing the systemic neglect of autistic women and gender-diverse individuals in autism research. By prioritizing their lived experience and perspectives, it challenges the dominance of male-centric research and highlights the urgent need for gender-sensitive, person-tailored mental health care. Given the increasing recognition of trauma's impact on autistic individuals, especially non-men, this research

develops knowledge on trauma-informed treatment. While existing studies establish the heightened vulnerability of this population, there is little exploration for treatments for PTSD in ASD populations. By identifying the efficacy and experience of mind-body therapies, this study may help clinicians move beyond conventional PTSD treatments, which may be ineffective for this group. Additionally, the study's focus on alternative therapeutic approaches could contribute to the growing movement toward tailored, inclusive mental health practices. It may also influence future policy and clinical guidelines, ensuring treatment accessibility to populations overlooked in autism research.

Due to the ethical requirements and broader certifications needed in order to conduct questionnaires and trials in this population, this author is unable to conduct even the preliminary interviews. Therefore, through research and expert interviews, a study proposal outlining the research and methodology that can be used by certified researchers in the future is provided as the final product of this thesis.

1. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW:

Pragmatism is ideal for this project as it allows for flexibility in addressing both practical and theoretical concerns. Pragmatism encourages a focus on solving real-world problems by using the most effective tools and methods available, rather than strictly adhering to a single methodological framework. It enables the integration of qualitative and quantitative approaches guided by the research problem, making it well-suited for mixed-methods research (Dawadi et al., 2021). The value of both subjective (lived experience) and objective (quantitative outcomes of the trials) data are recognised and contribute to the understanding of the efficacy, feasibility, implementation and perception of the mind-body therapies in this population.

This proposal uses the term 'autistic individuals' (identity-first language), as qualitative literature shows that autistic people prefer identity-first language, however, consensus is unclear (Hull et al., 2020; Taboas et al., 2022). "People with autism" has been found to be most offensive for autistic people (For why language matters in this case specifically see; Taboas et al., 2022 and Botha et al., 2023).

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by differences in social communication, sensory processing, and behavioural patterns (Carpita et al., 2024). Until very recently, ASD research focused predominantly on cisgender males, especially male children, revealing a significant gap in understanding the experiences of women and gender-diverse adults. Emerging evidence suggests that autism presents differently in these populations, often leading to underdiagnosis or misdiagnosis. In fact, autism has a male to female ratio of 4:1, which becomes 10:1 when there is no intellectual impairment, proposing a difference in presentation of autism, gender bias or biological difference in manifestation of autism (Carpita et al., 2024). Women are also diagnosed much later than men on average, despite the same number of professionals visited and age when parents first took them to said professionals (Carpita et al., 2024; Belcher et al., 2023). While some argue this may be due to biological differences, dubbed the 'female protective effect', this has not been confirmed by research (Gesi et al., 2021). Studies have found that autistic women are more likely to have better socio-communicative skills (reciprocal conversation, imaginative play, range of facial expressions and social awareness/motivation), increased masking and less repetitive and stereotyped behaviours than autistic men (Gesi et al., 2021; Beggiato et al., 2016; Belcher et al., 2022; Hiller et al., 2014). However, many gender related factors

such as difference in upbringing, enhanced camouflaging/'masking' and gendered socialisation may significantly contribute to this difference. Women may exhibit more socially acceptable and gender /age stereotyped interests and behaviours, in contrast to having less of these interests/behaviours (Gesi et al., 2021; Beggiano et al., 2016). Relational interests (such as in psychology, animals, relationships, TV) are found more often in autistic women than autistic men, and are closer to the interests of non-autistic women (Bourson et al., 2022; Hull et al., 2020). This may allow them to emulate non-autistic women and mask more (Belcher et al., 2023). Furthermore, autistic women tend to internalise their ASD symptoms in comparison to men who tend to externalise their symptoms, enforcing male-dominated presentations of autism (for example, shy/anxious/passive women falling more in line with gendered stereotypes) (Hull et al., 2020).

As autism is characterised as a social disorder, these differences in core traits and presentations could highly impact the impression and diagnosis of autism from a clinician perspective. Diagnosis of autism in women is made especially difficult by the male dominated diagnostic criteria and medical stigma leading to misdiagnosis, often as an eating disorder or borderline personality disorder (Carpita, et al., 2024; Belcher et al., 2022; Bargiela et al., 2016). Autistic women have to present with much more challenging behavioural problems in order to get a diagnosis, compared to autistic men (Belcher et al., 2022; Bargiela et al., 2016). The clinical and research gender bias in autism is visible in all aspects from diagnostic processes to research gaps, with clinicians and psychologists referencing this as a large barrier for autistic women (McLinden & Sedgewick, 2023; Hull et al., 2020). Furthermore, the difference in presentation of autism may contribute to unique mental health challenges and comorbidity, including increased vulnerability to anxiety, depression, suicidal ideation (especially when masking is high, as in autistic women) and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (Haruvi-Lamdan, et al., 2020; Beck, et al., 2020).

PTSD is a psychiatric condition triggered by exposure to traumatic events and is characterized by symptoms such as intrusive memories, hyperarousal, emotional dysregulation, and avoidance behaviours (Rumball et al., 2021). Research indicates that autistic individuals, particularly women and gender-diverse people, may be disproportionately affected by trauma due to factors such as memory difficulties, heightened sensory sensitivities, social vulnerability and miscommunication, cognitive inflexibility, medical neglect (including caregiver maltreatment) and difficulties in processing and expressing emotions and events (Rumball et al., 2021; Hernández-González, et al., 2023; Haruvi-Lamdan, et al., 2020; Junewicz, et al., 2024). ASD populations are significantly more likely to experience peer victimisation, violence, maltreatment and physical, sexual and emotional abuse (as well as poly-victimisation or cumulative trauma) than non-autistic people (Gibbs et al, 2021; Reuben et al, 2021; Haruvi-Lamdan et al., 2020). A large study of over 600 adults (including 230 cisgender men) with ASD found that up to 72% of them experienced sexual and/or physical assault (Reuben et al., 2021). This is corroborated by other studies reporting at least 45% of their ASD sample reporting some kind of violence, more than double the average in the general population (Gibbs et al., 2021, Nirit Haruvi-Lamdan et al., 2020).

Some studies report up to 61% probable lifetime PTSD and 45% current PTSD in ASD individuals with DSM-5 trauma exposure (compared to 5% lifetime PTSD for non-autistic people with the same trauma exposure). Interestingly, this figure stays relatively similar for non-DSM-5 trauma exposure in autistic individuals, showing a difference in how and when trauma is perceived in autistic and non-autistic populations (Rumball, et al., 2020; Rumball, et al., 2021). Moreover, autistic people have been shown to be less likely to confide in others, report

violence and rely on social supports which contributes significantly to PTSD development (Gibbs, et al., 2021, Haruvi-Lamdan, et al., 2021).

Furthermore, Reuben and colleagues (2021) found that autistic women and gender-diverse people are significantly more likely to have sexual traumas and a higher number of interpersonal traumas in general than autistic men. Transgender people also have an increased risk of experiencing sexual violence, partner violence, and/or assault (Cogan et al., 2021). Other studies corroborate these findings. Haruvi-Lamdan and colleagues found that autistic women are at greater risk for exposure to traumatic events (especially in the social sphere such as through physical and sexual assaults) and for the development of post-traumatic stress symptoms (PTSS) (2021). Carpita and colleagues (2019) also found higher trauma symptom scores in autistic women compared to other groups (non-autistic males and females and autistic males).

These findings may contribute to higher rates of PTSD in these populations. In fact, Reuben and colleagues (2021) showed that autistic women are significantly more likely than autistic men to meet the criteria for PTSD. Their study also found that non binary and trans individuals were the most likely to meet the criteria for PTSD in their sample (compared to cisgender men and women). Another systematic review found that the prevalence of PTSD goes down when studies include more male autistic participants (Rumball et al., 2019).

However, rates of PTSD in ASD populations vary greatly between studies. While there is a large variety under the ASD umbrella, interpersonal differences do not wholly account for this variation. Reasons for this variety include lack of in depth screening and diagnostic instruments for autistic people, lack of reliable studies measuring PTSD symptoms in autistic adults (especially in women) and methodological differences (such as only including treatment-seeking/trauma exposed ASD populations) (Junewicz, et al., 2024). Reliable diagnostic instruments for the ASD population need to be researched as trauma symptoms may present very differently in ASD populations, within group and compared to other populations. Currently there are no validated measures for the assessment of trauma symptoms in autistic people, although the PTSD section of the Autism Adapted Anxiety Disorder Interview Schedule for children (ASA/ADIS-C) has been found to be reliable (Lobregt-van Buuren et al., 2019).

Autistic people have been shown to be more likely than non-autistic people to 1) perceive a broader range of events as traumatic (seen also in the significant amount of non-DSM-5 traumas reported), 2) develop and experience more distressing trauma symptoms (especially in hyper-arousal and re-experiencing clusters) and 3) manifest trauma symptoms differently (ex. Language regression, aggression, self-injury) (Junewicz et al., 2024; Peterson et al., 2019). Studies on samples of autistic children with trauma exposure have shown “development of new behavioural difficulties (e.g., aggression, self-injury, agitation), increased stereotypies, worsening social-communication impairments, increased distractibility/hyperactivity, alterations in sleep and appetite, and decline in self-help skills” (Peterson et al., 2019, p.534). These symptoms may be confounding and may exacerbate ASD symptoms and therefore be overlooked by clinicians and screening tools (Kildahl et al., 2020).

Treatment strategies for ASD populations generally focus on promotion of neurotypical development and reducing the impact of core ASD symptoms through behavioural approaches (Fuld, 2018). Strategies that target mental health or quality of life are overlooked in ASD research and treatment, and trauma intervention studies are almost completely absent (Fuld, 2018). Conventional PTSD treatments, such as Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) and Exposure Therapy, may not be well-suited for autistic individuals (Peterson et al., 2019).

These methods often rely on cognitive restructuring and verbal processing, which can be particularly difficult for autistic people. They are designed with non-autistic individuals in mind, and may not fully accommodate the sensory sensitivities, communication issues, alexithymia (difficulty identifying and describing emotions), and cognitive processing differences that autistic people experience. However, alternative adapted interventions may be able to take these differences into account and use them to the therapy's advantage.

A systematic review in 2019 by Rumball and colleagues on studies for PTSD treatments in ASD populations revealed just 7 articles, most only including minors. This review found some studies on Trauma-Focused-CBT, an adapted CBT model, showing reduced PTSS in autistic children with PTSD (Rumball, 2019). Other articles focused on psychotherapy and pharmacological interventions with varying success. One case study focused on EMDR, with the client experiencing significant improvements and no longer meeting the criteria for PTSD, even after 3 months. To the knowledge of this author two more studies have been published since. This included one case study on a young boy who was treated with TF-CBT using his special interest within the narrative therapy and reported improvements in depressive symptoms and reduced trauma preservation (Gerhardt & Smith, 2020). The second study focused on Eye Movement Desensitisation and Reprocessing (EMDR) for ASD adults with a history of adverse events and found it to be effective in reducing PTSS and distress, with the effect being maintained at an 8 week follow up (Lobregt-van Buuren, E., et al. 2019). It seems that EMDR may be an effective and feasible intervention in this population.

Mind-body interventions, such as mindfulness, EMDR, and yoga, have been explored to address the needs of autistic individuals. However, these studies do not usually target trauma symptoms. A meta-analysis and systematic review on mind-body therapies for PTSD in the general population shows them to be highly effective, reporting significant reductions in PTSS, depression and anxiety and improved sleep and mental well-being (Zhu et al., 2022; Kiep, 2014). This is corroborated by a meta-analysis done specifically on women who have experienced violence, reporting the same results (Koroglu & Durat, 2025).

Emphasizing a holistic connection between mental and physical well-being, as done in such mind-body therapies, may be particularly beneficial for those experiencing PTSD symptoms alongside ASD. This may also be due to the shift away from traditional cognitive processing therapies such as in CBT. Mind-body therapies may offer a sensory and cognitive accessibility that suits this population better. Moreover, studies have shown that autistic individuals are more likely to perceive their mind and body as one, possibly enhancing mind-body therapies in this population (Berent et al., 2022).

A systematic review conducted by Hourston and Atchley (2017) examined mind-body therapies in autistic individuals and found promising, albeit limited, evidence supporting their efficacy. The review included adapted interventions such as mindfulness-based cognitive therapy, yoga, and acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT). Studies on mindfulness-based interventions reported moderate to significant improvements in anxiety, depression and rumination which were maintained at a 9 week follow-up. Similarly, yoga-based interventions demonstrated enhanced self-regulation and reduced behavioural issues. However, most studies included small sample sizes, lacked control groups, or did not specifically investigate gender differences. A more recent systematic review (Semple et al., 2019) found similar results, with yoga and mindfulness studies improving quality of life scores as well as a variety of prosocial behaviours. This review also found reductions in aggressive

behaviour, non-compliance, irritability and social withdrawal. These 8 preliminary studies provide promising results but suffer from many limitations and are not sufficient to provide conclusive evidence.

A randomised controlled study by Pahnke and colleagues (2022) found that an adapted version of ACT (NeuroACT) improved perceived quality of life, stress levels, inflexibility, and cognitive and behavioural avoidance in a small group of autistic adults (10:10 men: women). It also improved measures of autistic mannerisms on the social awareness scale. Dropout rates were slightly higher compared to treatment as usual, but the NeuroACT group was rated highly credible and feasible in this population. Another randomised controlled study on mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) in autistic adults found that autistic women (who have lower quality of life scores than autistic men and non-autistic people) improve the most on health and disability related quality of life scores after MBSR (Braden et al., 2022). Two studies by Lunsy and colleagues on group mindfulness-based interventions showed high feasibility and positive qualitative results on distress and compassion measures (2022). Their women-only group was particularly well received, with good feedback and slight decreases in psychological distress measures.

Strategies that target mental health or quality of life are overlooked in ASD research and treatment, and trauma intervention studies are almost completely absent (Fuld et al., 2018). Research on mind-body therapies in the autistic population are still limited in number and by small sample sizes, lack of control group, no formal diagnosis or other methodological limitations. Given that autistic women and gender-diverse people often experience trauma differently from men, there remains an even more significant gap in research examining the interplay between ASD in women, PTSD/PTSS, and mind-body therapies.

The next section will outline the pilot expert study conducted to add to the foundation of research on screening and treatment in this population. The study aims to contribute to our understanding of autism and trauma screening and treatment through the perspectives of clinicians.

2. EXPERT STUDY

METHODOLOGY

The pilot study was a Qualtrics survey conducted on experts (clinicians and educators) who work with autistic women and trauma symptoms. The full English survey can be found in the appendix (appendix item 1). The Dutch translation was done in collaboration with a Dutch university student and offered to the respondents on Qualtrics. Respondents were recruited through emailing organisations and centres who work with autistic people as well as through the snowball effect (a participant sends the link to their colleagues that align with the studies eligibility criteria). The survey took about 10 minutes to complete and was available in both English and Dutch. A survey was done due to time constraints and language barriers (the author does not speak Dutch fluently). Using a survey also gives the responder more time, reduces interviewer bias through standardised questions, reduces social desirability bias and enhances accessibility and convenience for participants (Hecker et al., 2023).

Descriptive data was recorded such as the kind of organisation, the kind of service they provide, their degree, their years of experience and how often they rate they work with autistic women or gender-diverse individuals (See Table 1). Then they were asked more open questions about their experience with and perception of trauma screening, experience and treatment throughout their career in this population. The open responses are

analysed through inductive thematic analysis on a semantic level through a data-driven approach (Braun & Clarke, 2006), coding for the direct description of what the experts report.

The author of this study emailed 80 different clinicians and educators, with a follow up email after two weeks, and got 10 responses in total. Responses were analysed to ensure quality responses, Qualtrics supplied a 100% score and the author checked each of these dimensions by hand (Straightlining, location data, bot/duplicate responses and unanswered questions). Three responses were omitted due to the responders not finishing the survey. Dutch responses were translated in collaboration with a Dutch university student.

Ethical Considerations

The preliminary expert surveys should not encounter any ethical problems. However, as the topic may bring up sensitive experiences for the expert, some discomfort could arise. A consent form will be filled out before the survey begins. This will declare the purpose of the study, potentially triggering questions and what contributions the experts provide to the study. The fact that they can withdraw from the survey at any time will be mentioned too. They will be informed that their responses will be recorded and stored securely to be coded for this project, after which they will be deleted (by the 10th of June 2025). Pseudonyms will be used during coding, writing and processes of feedback in which any third party will look at the project. This will ensure their anonymity, however, if additional information is deemed to be identifiable (like the name of their private practice), this too will be given a pseudonym or omitted completely.

Potential benefits can be reaped by the experts. The survey could increase their awareness of their own personal biases, knowledge gaps and of potential new treatment recommendations for this population. This may spark interest into developing their knowledge by researching trauma screening and treatment, and therefore benefit their clients too. Useful references will be provided in the survey further increasing the chances of them researching the topic.

RESULTS

Quantitative Data

Descriptive Table for Respondents			
Organisation		N	%
	Private practice	4	57.1%
	Hospital	1	14.3%
	Mental health centre or clinic	2	28.6%
Role			
	Psychologist	5	71.4%
	Psychotherapist	1	14.3%
	Trauma therapist	1	14.3%
Experience			

	<1	1	14.3%
	1-5	2	28.6%
	6-10	2	28.6%
	>10	2	28.6%
Degree			
	Masters	5	71.4%
	Doctorate	2	28.6%
Patient Age			
	Under 18	1	14.3%
	Only Adults	3	42.9%
	All Ages	3	42.9%
Frequency working with ASD			
	Rarely	1	14.3%
	Sometimes	2	28.6%
	Often	2	28.6%
	Always	2	28.6%
Frequency working with ASD Women/GDI			
	Rarely	1	14.3%
	Sometimes	3	42.9%
	Often	3	42.9%
Trained in Trauma Screening			
	Yes, during my education	3	42.9%
	Yes, during my career	2	28.6%
	Unsure	2	28.6%

Table 1. Table of Descriptive Characteristics of the Survey Respondents

Most respondents were part of a private practice (4/7) as a psychologist (5/7) and had been working with autistic people at least sometimes (6/7) for over one year (6/7). Furthermore, 5/7 of respondents reported rarely/never working with autistic people with intellectual disabilities. Internalising problems were the most common issues reported to be presented to the experts by autistic people (6/7), with one respondent focusing only on trauma related problems (this respondent worked at a trauma clinic). 5/7 Respondents had been formally trained in trauma screening either during their education or career and inquired about trauma history in all of their autistic patients. However, 3/7 respondents reported not formally screening for trauma in their autistic patients when there was

suspected trauma history, with two of the three being those who reported being unsure of their training in trauma screening. Among those that screened for trauma in at least most of their autistic patients (4/7), inquiry of physical or emotional neglect, domestic violence, physical or emotional abuse and parent mental illness was reported for all autistic patients.

	Some	Most	All	Most or More
Inquiry – Trauma History	28.6%		71.4%	71.4%
Inquiry – Physical and/or emotional neglect	14.3%	14.3%	71.4%	85.7%
Inquiry – Emotional Abuse	14.3%	14.3%	71.4%	85.7%
Inquiry – Physical or Sexual Abuse	14.3%	14.3%	71.4%	85.7%
Inquiry – Domestic Violence		14.3%	85.7%	100.0%
Inquiry – Parent Mental Illness		28.6%	71.4%	100.0%

Table 2. Summary of responses to Q11-Q12.5. *“In what proportion of your autistic patients/clients/students do you inquire about;”*

Formal Screening	Yes	No
	57.1%	42.9%

Table 3. Summary of responses to Q13. *“Do you use formal screening methods when there are suspected trauma-related symptoms in your autistic patients/clients/students?”*

	None	Some	Most	All	Some or More
Formal Screening	14.3%	28.6%	28.6%	28.6%	85.7%
Treatment	42.9%		14.3%	42.9%	57.1%

Table 3. Summary of responses to Q14.1 and Q14.2 *“In what proportion of your autistic patients/ clients/students do you provide;”*

Descriptive characteristics for the opinion questions were generated in JASP, providing the means, standard deviations (both with confidence intervals), skewness and kurtosis. This table can be found in the appendix (appendix table 4). The most consensus in the opinion questions was found for A/D 2 (“Autistic women and gender-diverse people experience trauma differently”) and, A/D 1 (“Autistic traits impact how trauma symptoms manifest”). These responses ranged from ‘strongly agree’ to ‘somewhat agree’ and ‘neither agree nor disagree’ to ‘somewhat agree’ respectively (means of 4.429 and 3.571 respectively) with a low standard deviation (0.535) from these means. Other strong opinions were seen in the question A/D 4 (“It is not possible to identify trauma-related symptoms in autistic people”), with 6/7 respondents answering ‘strongly disagree’ (mean of 1.429). There seemed to be further consensus on the question A/D 5 (“Lack of training is a barrier to identifying trauma-related symptoms in autistic people”) with most (5/7) responses being at least ‘somewhat agree’ and the other two being ‘neither agree nor disagree’ (mean of 4). A/D 6 (“There is a lack of treatment options for this population”) had 4/7 respondents reporting at least ‘somewhat agree’. The least consensus could be found in question A/D 7 (“Traditional trauma treatments are insufficient for this population”) with answers ranging widely from ‘strongly disagree’ to ‘somewhat agree’ (mean of 2.857, range 1-4). A/D 3 (“The tools we have to screen for trauma in

autistic people are insufficient”) also had a low consensus, with answers ranging widely from ‘strongly disagree’ to ‘somewhat agree’ (mean of 3.286, range 2-5).

	Valid	Missing	Mean	95% Confidence Interval Mean		Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
				Upper	Lower			
A/D_1	7	0	4.429	4.923	3.934	0.535	4.000	5.000
A/D_2	7	0	3.571	4.066	3.077	0.535	3.000	4.000
A/D_3	7	0	3.286	4.315	2.257	1.113	2.000	5.000
A/D_4	7	0	1.429	2.156	0.701	0.787	1.000	3.000
A/D_5	7	0	4.000	4.755	3.245	0.816	3.000	5.000
A/D_6	7	0	3.571	4.474	2.669	0.976	2.000	5.000
A/D_7	7	0	2.857	3.846	1.868	1.069	1.000	4.000

Table 4. Descriptive characteristics generated through JASP for opinion questions in expert survey.

Qualitative Data

Respondents reported using a diverse range of treatment approaches for autistic patients with trauma history including art psychotherapy, breathwork, play therapy, internal family systems therapy, holistic/humanistic/client centred therapy (2 mentions), EMDR (2 mentions), narrative exposure, prolonged exposure, imagery rescripting, dialectical behavioural therapy and solution focused therapy. Open responses on questions 16 and 17 were thematically analysed on a semantic level to produce a multitude of themes that emerge from the data. The research question was as follows; How do experts view the intersection between trauma and autism?

Three separate themes were coded from the responses to Q16 and Q17, 1) Autism is a heterogeneous concept, 2) Tailored treatments may be needed in some cases and 3) Autistic traits may affect other aspects of mental health. Theme 1 was coded for 7 times and was present in 3 of 5 responses. One respondent (R3, a psychologist with 6-10 years of experience with ASD) acknowledged the variety of difference within this population in regards to response to treatment. Another respondent, a psychotherapist (R5), also brought up this theme; they explained that there are very large differences in response to treatment at the individual level, between all people and even more so within the group of people “who we say have autism... remember autism is not concrete, it is a concept” [translated from Dutch]. They explain their belief that autism has become such a heterogeneous concept that it has become difficult to say anything in general terms about client characteristics of this group.

The second theme was coded for 5 times and was present in 3 of 5 responses. One respondent (R5) stated that “Traditional treatment methods can sometimes be less effective, but they can also be remarkably effective”. Another (R3) reported that they believe many people within the GGZ (mental health care field) have autistic traits and therefore the treatments offered are often already tailored to this population. A third respondent answered that “unless you see clear contraindications based on individual client characteristics, I would start with regular treatment methods.” [translated from Dutch], specifying that autistic people do not necessarily need different treatments but they may react differently than expected and might need specific accommodations due to their greater sensitivity.

The last code was present in 2 of 5 responses. One respondent (R3) stated that “Because people with autism are more sensitive I think they are also more sensitive to trauma” [translated from Dutch]. The second respondent (R2) agreed that while autism may not be the primary problem at registration, it does seem to affect the treatment and experience of the primary problem.

Due to the limited size of the pilot study, no true statistical tests were performed on the data. Normality and equal variances were violated in almost every case. However, the responses still contribute to our understanding of screening and treatment of trauma in this population and clinician perspectives on different aspects of interest within this field.

DISCUSSION

This pilot study provided initial insight into expert perspectives on trauma experience, screening and treatment among autistic people. Despite the small sample size ($n=7$), the responses revealed both quantitative trends and qualitative depth, contributing to the foundational understanding needed to further this research. The insights gained from this study directly contribute to refining the proposed interview guides, identifying key themes of inquiry (such as the perceived insufficiency of existing screening tools and treatment modalities). Additionally, the thematic findings help validate the conceptual basis of the project by supporting the research found previously. Especially the idea that existing clinical frameworks may not fully address the needs of this population, thereby reinforcing the relevance and necessity of developing autism-informed, trauma-sensitive therapeutic models. Furthermore, two respondents specifically thanked the author for the additional references given and mentioned that the survey led them to do more research on trauma in this population, adding to its clinical relevance and contribution.

The descriptive data suggested that most participants were psychologists with substantial experience working with autistic individuals (including autistic women and gender diverse people) and were professionally trained in trauma screening. This aligns with the study's recruitment focus on experienced clinicians and educators. Practices regarding trauma screening and treatment varied among the clinicians. For example, while the majority (71%) reported that they inquire about trauma history in all autistic patients, 43% did not use formal screening tools and only 28% universally screened for trauma. This discrepancy was most apparent among those who were unsure of their training in trauma screening, indicating that these training gaps may directly impact clinical practice. These findings support results from previous expert studies in this field by Kerns et al, (2019) who found that while 70% of clinicians informally assess for trauma in ASD populations, only 10% universally screen for it. While we did not ask about confidence in own trauma knowledge, 71% of respondents reported being trained in trauma screening either in their career or education, higher than other reported percentages (Ahlers et al., 2019). However, most clinicians did agree that lack of training is a barrier to identifying trauma-related symptoms in autistic people. Moreover, the lack of consensus on the sufficiency of trauma screening tools in this population relates to this theme too. Those who agreed on the insufficiency of these tools had over 10 years of experience with autistic people, adding to existing literature that highlights the lack of standardised and evidence-based trauma screening protocols adapted for autistic populations (Rumball et al., 2021; Peterson et al., 2019).

Most clinicians agreed that there are a lack of trauma treatment options for ASD populations. A total of 12 different therapies were reportedly used, with EMDR and holistic therapies being the most popular. Clinicians acknowledged that while traditional treatments can be effective, they may require modification based on individual sensitivities and clinical presentations. Many brought up the large differences within the autism population and the need for treatment models to be a adaptable and person-centred. This was rooted in the need to consider how autistic traits like heightened sensitivity may influence the processing and expression of trauma

and thereby, of treatment. Responses showed strong agreement that autistic traits influence trauma symptom manifestation and that autistic women and gender-diverse individuals experience trauma differently. Most respondents strongly disagreed that it was impossible to identify trauma-related symptoms in autistic people, with one strongly disagreeing outlier. One respondent stated the trauma screening tools they use for this population (none were autism-adapted); the PCL-5 and LEC-5 [explained in the appendix glossary]. These points reflect the aforementioned research on autism and PTSD as well as gender-based disparities in autism diagnosis, perception and experience of trauma (Belcher et al., 2022; Haruvi-Lamdan et al., 2020). This aligns with emerging calls for autism-informed care models that can flexibly integrate individual needs, as well as previous expert studies in this field (Fuld et al., 2018; Pahnke et al., 2023; Ahlers et al., 2019).

There are several limitations to this expert study. Using convenience sampling increases the risk of self-selection bias, affecting the representativeness of the findings. While this cannot be avoided, a larger sample size and recruitment from many different organisations may decrease this bias. The reliance on a survey still risks social desirability bias as well as restricted response depth, as closed-ended questions may not fully capture participants' perspectives. To reduce this, the survey emphasises their anonymity, the need for honesty in their responses, uses indirect questioning and multiple questions asking similar things (Ried et al., 2022). Limitations may still arise as survey questions may be misinterpreted or not previously validated in this context. There is not enough research for standardised questionnaires to be used, however a previous expert study by Kerns and colleagues on a similar topic was used as reference for the interview guide (2020). The low response rate ($n=7$) limits the generalisability of the findings and underscores the challenges of engaging busy professionals in survey-based research. Further limitations can be found in the appendix. Despite these limitations, the high-quality responses coupled with the statistical and thematic analysis provided a strong preliminary foundation for understanding clinical perspectives in this area and future methodological adaptations in this project.

To further develop the projects suggestions on trial methodologies for trauma treatment in autism populations, a scoping review is outlined in the next section. This review is conducted on the methodologies of mind-body treatments in autistic populations, with and without trauma symptoms, to develop a concrete overview.

3. SCOPING REVIEW

INTRODUCTION

Autistic individuals are disproportionately affected by trauma, with significantly higher rates (and instances) of exposure to adverse events such as interpersonal violence, abuse, neglect, and medical neglect than non-autistic people. Autistic women and gender-diverse individuals are at an even greater risk of experiencing trauma, especially in the form of social and sexual victimisation, and are more likely to develop PTSD/PTSS (Reuben et al., 2021; Haruvi-Lamdan et al., 2020). There remains a scarcity of research on trauma interventions for this population, despite this heightened vulnerability. Conventional trauma therapies may be inadequate in addressing the specific cognitive, emotional, and sensory needs of autistic individuals (Peterson et al., 2019). Adaptations to these therapies or alternative therapies are most often needed for this population.

Autism-adapted mind-body therapies (MBTs) have gained interest as potentially effective alternatives. These approaches emphasise holistic wellbeing and may be more accessible to autistic people who face challenges

with verbal communication, emotional regulation, and somatic awareness. Preliminary evidence suggests that MBTs can improve symptoms of PTSD, anxiety, and depression in both the general population and autistic adults. They may be particularly promising for women and gender-diverse individuals (Zhu et al., 2022; Hourston & Atchley, 2017; Braden et al., 2022). However, the methodological approaches used in these studies vary widely in terms of intervention design, outcome measures, adaptation strategies, and population specificity. There is currently no clear overview of how mind-body therapies have been employed in autistic populations, how they have been adapted to meet neurodivergent needs, or to what extent studies have considered the experiences of autistic women and gender-diverse individuals.

In light of this, a scoping literature review using the Arksey and O'Malley framework (Peters et al., 2020) is conducted to examine the methodology of studies for mind-body treatments in ASD populations. A scoping review allows the author to write a comprehensive overview of specifically the methodologies in a short period of time (Munn et al., 2018). This will help to inform the methodology of the final proposed studies on mind-body therapies for PTSD in ASD populations. Given the limited and varying nature of the literature in this area, a scoping review is the most appropriate method to systematically map what is known, identify how studies have been conducted, and inform the methodology for the future studies. The central research question guiding this review is: What methodologies have been used in the study of mind-body therapies for autistic individuals with trauma histories? Sub-questions further explore the types of mind-body interventions that have been studied, the adaptations made to suit autistic participants, the extent to which autistic women and gender-diverse individuals are included or addressed, and the range of outcomes and measures employed. Together, these questions aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of research in this area, identify promising directions, and highlight critical gaps that the future studies must address.

METHODOLOGY

This scoping review follows the PRISMA ScR checklist (available in the appendix) to ensure it is in line with the standard. All screening is done by one reviewer using Covidence. This review only considers studies done within the last 15 years in order to maintain some level of standardisation within treatment practices and reflect more contemporary understandings of autism. Due to the language spoken by the reviewer, only English studies are considered. Clinical trials are prioritised to maintain the usefulness of this review for the proposed randomised, controlled trials. Other types of studies were included such as pilot studies, qualitative studies, reviews, expert studies and case reports to enrich this scoping review. Studies on autistic adults with or without a formal diagnosis are included to widen the scope but keep within the target population. Studies done on children and adolescents were excluded. Studies that investigate mind-body therapies will be targeted, especially when as an intervention for trauma or trauma-related symptoms. This includes; mindfulness-based interventions (MBSR, MBCT), Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT or NeuroACT), yoga or movement-based therapies, EMDR (Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing), breathwork, meditation, or other somatic techniques. Studies must at least include outcomes related to PTSS or PTSD, anxiety/distress related to trauma, and/or quality of life/wellbeing. The databases used were as follows; Web of Science, PubMed and PsycINFO. The search strategy is built off of previous studies that reviewed a similar topic (Rumball et al., 2019; Quinton et al., 2024)

Date Used	Database	Search String
23/04/25	Web of Science	treatment* OR mindfulness OR "mindfulness-based" OR MBSR OR MBCT OR "Acceptance and Commitment" OR ACT OR NeuroACT OR yoga OR EMDR OR "Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing" OR breathwork OR meditation (Topic) and Trauma* OR PTSD or PTSS OR post-traumatic OR "post traumatic" OR posttraumatic OR "adverse experience*" OR ADE OR distress (Topic) and Autis* OR asperger* OR PDD-NOS OR ASD OR "Autism Spectrum" (Topic) and English (Language)

Table 5. Search Strategy Overview for Scoping Review

As previous searches have shown a lack of research in this area, studies that used mind-body therapies in general in ASD populations (not trauma focused) were also included. These are analysed separately to add to the methodology development from the trauma focused mind-body studies. To extract data we focused on multiple different features of the study, especially the methodology. Simple study characteristics were recorded such as design, recruitment strategies and aim/purpose. Population characteristics that were important to note were sample size, age range, gender distribution (as well as inclusion of non-binary genders), living situation and diagnosis status. For the trauma intervention studies, trauma type and assessment (PTSD diagnosis, trauma questionnaire etc.) was recorded. Then the intervention types were recorded and analysed according to their duration, frequency, setting and delivery. Any adaptations made for the autistic populations were recorded. The outcomes of each study were extracted, including the tools used to measure these outcomes. Main findings including feasibility (dropout rates, adherence etc.) and limitations were assessed and recorded. An extraction template is available in the appendix (appendix table 5). To report this data, we use descriptive statistics and some basic thematic coding of qualitative studies.

RESULTS

Study Selection

The search returned 74 results, with three extra articles being found in citations of these searches, of which 13 were duplicates. The reviewer did two screens, at the title/abstract screening stage 51 articles were removed. These were removed due to not being the right publication type (conference transcripts for example), intervention (pharmacological interventions) and/or population (children or intellectually disabled only). One study could not be retrieved due to lack of institutional access. 11 studies were moved to full text screening and assessed for eligibility, of which 2 were excluded due to wrong design (letter to editor) and wrong population. 9 studies were included in the final review and fulfilled the inclusion criteria. These varied in nature, with some being intervention trials with a mindfulness strategy for PTSD or for other complaints, and others being expert studies or reviews. The full PRISMA flowchart can be seen in figure 2 and the study characteristics can be found below.

Figure 2. PRISMA Flowchart Generated in Covidence and Edited by the Author.

Intervention Trials

The trials included in this review were either produced during screening or by extracting articles from previous reviews (Rumball, 2019; Hourston et al., 2017; Quinton et al., 2023). Only those within the reviews that fit our inclusion and exclusion criteria were used. This left us with 7 trials, namely Lobregt-van Buuren et al. (2019), Spek et al., (2013), Braden et al., (2022), Kiep et al., (2014), Pahnke et al., (2023), Lunksy et al., (2022), Redquest et al., (2022). A full overview of the data extracted can be found in the appendix (appendix table 6 and 7). There were three randomised controlled studies, one non randomised add on study, and three cohort studies. Most studies recruited patients referred from the outpatient service for a single autism centre/ clinic. Only one had a focus on autistic people with suspected PTSD, which they assessed through the ADIS-C PTSD section. However many studies recruited participants who were referred by their clinicians as having symptoms of depression, anxiety and/or rumination. Sample sizes were generally small (range of 20-55) and contained mostly men (mean of 61.5%, one outlier study had only women and was removed from this mean). Only one study (Lunsky et al, 2022) included non-binary as a gender option, making up 5% of their sample. Most studies allowed medication use with no changes and included comorbid populations due to the high variety and comorbidity found in ASD populations. Common exclusion criteria were current mania or psychosis, substance abuse, other neurodevelopmental

disorders, institutionalisation and intellectual disability. Many studies included self-identified autistic people (those reporting any ASD diagnosis), however some studies also required a clinical interview and questionnaires to confirm this (AQ, SRS, WURS).

One study looked at EMDR (Lobregt-van Buuren et al., 2019), one at NeuroACT (Pahnke et al., 2023), three at MBSR (mindfulness-based stress reduction)(Braden et al., 2022; Lunsky et al., 2022; Redquest et al., 2022), and two at MBT-AS (Autism-adapted mindfulness-based therapy) (Kiep et al., 2014; Spek et al., 2013). There was a large variety (range of 3-14) of frequency of sessions in different studies, most sessions were around 2hrs with individual homework strongly encouraged. Control groups were used in some studies, either as a waitlist or treatment as usual (or both consecutively). Treatment as usual consisted of general support/education offered for autistic populations such as psychotherapy, psychoeducation, supportive counselling and/or job counselling. Adaptations for ASD populations were present in all studies. The most common adaptations were; using more concrete language, omitting cognitive elements of protocols, not requiring retreats, having additional sessions (although two studies specifically outlined less sessions as being an adaptation) and having optional sessions. Guidance for the sessions was done by trained practitioners of the respective treatment. Two studies outlined the benefit (according to the participants) of having an autistic practitioner for the classes (Lunsky et al., 2022; Redquest et al., 2022).

Psychological distress [symptoms of depression and anxiety] was an outcome in nearly all studies (6/7), assessed by the SCL-90-R (2 studies), BSI, MINI, BDI-II, BAI, and DASS-21 (2 studies). Other common outcomes included autistic core traits (AS, SRS, SRS-A), rumination (RRQ), quality of life (QoLI, WHO-QoL-BREF), feasibility (AD-TCS), intervention satisfaction (SCS-SF) and mindfulness (FFMQ-SF). Feasibility and intervention satisfaction were high in all studies. Only one study reported insignificant results (Redquest et al., 2022), with most reporting significant improvements in all outcomes after their interventions. One study (Braden et al., 2022) reported varying results by gender, with women benefitting more from MBSR in the health related quality of life outcome. A lot of limitations were reported by the different studies. The most common were; small sample sizes, use of self-reports, sample of adults with average to high verbal abilities, no real control or waitlist, unvalidated assessment measures for outcomes in this population and self-identification of autism.

Expert Study and Review

The expert study and review included helped to inform further adaptations that may be needed in the methodology. The review by Peterson and colleagues (2019) has an in depth outline of adaptations to trauma focused cognitive behavioural therapy (TF-CBT) as well as psychoeducation for autistic patients. This will form the foundation for the proposed control group in the trials. The expert study on EMDR in autistic individuals (Fisher et al., 2022) highlighted adaptations, barriers and aspects of clinical supervision of EMDR that are important to understand to develop the methodology of the proposed trials. The adaptations followed three core principles of flexibility and patient involvement, clear and diverse communication and awareness of individual differences. Experts reported the importance of 1) clinician expertise in autism and other neurodevelopmental disorders; 2) patient understanding of flexibility of therapy; and 3) time to discuss therapeutic relationship, approach, adaptations and challenges. Two important barriers that should be addressed in the proposed study were also outlined. For one, therapist characteristics like lack of confidence, training and knowledge on methods of clear communication with

this population were acknowledged. Secondly, differences in the understanding and building of the therapeutic relationship were also reported.

CONCLUSION

There are several limitations for this scoping review. All screening, data extraction, and quality appraisal were conducted by a single reviewer. While internal consistency was good, this also increases the risk of subjective interpretation and selection bias. Furthermore, despite the focus on autistic women and gender-diverse individuals, few studies analysed data by gender or included non-binary participants. Most samples were predominantly male, and only one study reported non-binary inclusion. However, this limitation also adds to how the proposed trials may progress our current knowledge.

This scoping review outlines both the methodologies and the current limitations of mind-body therapies for autistic adults with trauma histories. The relevant information from the above studies is further discussed through design of the proposed methodologies below.

4.A PROPOSED METHODOLOGY FOR INTERVIEWS

The proposed semi-structured interviews are crucial for enabling person-informed, autistic-tailored therapies, where participants in the trials have their lived experience taken into account and receive trauma-sensitive persona-tailored treatments. These will be conducted before, during and after the trials to assess the feasibility, implementation and perception of the adapted mind-body therapies. These sessions also give time to discuss the therapeutic relationship, approach, adaptations and challenges. These qualitative results are necessary to enhance the generality and nuance in the study's findings as well as to inform future studies. Furthermore, the preliminary interviews act as a screening and recruitment for the trials that will take place.

The eligibility criteria are the same as the trials. Namely, people with a clinical diagnosis of Aspergers or ASD without intellectual or language impairment were invited to participate. The exclusion criteria are 1) having current mania and/or psychosis and/or substance abuse (over three months); 2) being a minor; 3) having an intellectual disability; 4) having been institutionalised; 5) no formal diagnosis of any ASD; 6) no trauma history; 7) changes to medication use within the last 3 months.

A questionnaire template is outside the scope of this project. However, some resources are given for potential use in the building of the questionnaire [cite].

4.B PROPOSED METHODOLOGY FOR TRIALS

DESIGN

The overall investigation comprises of three randomized two-group controlled trials, each evaluating one mind-body therapy (EMDR, MBSR, or ACT) against treatment-as-usual (TAU). This trial will use stratified block-wise randomisation in which each strata (men, women, gender diverse individuals) are allocated 1:1 to either control or treatment blocks. This allows us to keep the same sample size in all groups while maintaining a balance of covariates (possible confounders like gender) (Kang et al., 2008). The blocks are allocated by separating the strata and handing out a container full of mixed folded pieces of paper (either 'treatment' or 'control') for each

participant to choose from. Then the treatment and control strata are separated and allocated 1:1:1:1, using the same paper method, to either EMDR, MBSR, ACT or TAU. The stratified method is better for smaller sample sizes (<100) and for studies with a low amount of covariates, like this one (Kang et al., 2008).

The format facilitates inclusion of a broad spectrum of outcome measures, covering PTSD severity, psychological distress, sleep, stress, mindfulness skills and quality of life, to comprehensively assess therapeutic impact. Feasibility and satisfaction will also be measured to further the development of these protocols in the future. Repeated measures will be obtained at pre-treatment (T1), immediately post-treatment (T2), and three months post-treatment (T3) to evaluate both short- and longer-term effects. Post-treatment assessments will occur within one week of intervention completion, aligning with standard study intervals.

ETHICS

The whole study must be approved by ethics committee of the region/country the study will take place, the ethical requirements might therefore change slightly. For the sake of transparency, all participants will be informed of the data collection processes and their right to withdraw from the study at any time through written and verbal communication. They will be asked to sign the written consent form. When working with autistic populations with trauma history, we must keep in mind the specific and individual differences that occur in this population. To maintain sensitivity throughout the trial process this author, as well as previous studies, strongly recommends having at least one autistic researcher in the team. Moreover, previous studies recommend that the clinicians administering the therapies should also be autistic.

PARTICIPANTS

Participants will be recruited through the interviews, as well as agencies, clinics and centres that work with autistic people (in assessment, treatment or education). People with a clinical diagnosis of Aspergers or ASD without intellectual or language impairment were invited to participate. To be eligible for the trials you must 1) not have current mania and/or psychosis and/or substance abuse (over three months); 2) be over the age of 18 years; 3) not have an intellectual disability; 4) not have been institutionalised; 5) be formally diagnosed with any ASD; 6) have trauma history; 7) if using medication, must have no changes three months before trials. To increase the generalisability of the findings and be more representative of the autistic population, autistic people with comorbid neurodevelopmental disorders (eg. ADHD) will not be excluded from the studies. Common descriptive data will be recorded such as diagnosis, race, age, comorbidity, education, medication dosage, living situation, socio-economic status. Gender identity will be recorded in 6 fields; women, men, trans men, trans women, non-binary, other.

ASSESSMENT

Diagnostic assessment will be done by experienced clinicians and follow the general protocol in the country the study is undertaken. Each participant will be clinically interviewed by a psychologist, along with at least one of their close family members or friends. Then they are given self-rated questionnaires to assess their autistic core symptoms. The Adult Autism Spectrum Quotient (AQ) is a standardised measure in this population. Then the

feasibility and satisfaction with the intervention will be self-rated through questionnaires given by the clinicians. The participants will then finally go through qualitative interviews to gain further insight into their lived experience of the interventions, building on the data for feasibility, satisfaction and perception. Assessment of PTSD symptoms is done through the ADIS-C-PTSD Section, with > 4 points being evidence of PTSD, and through the PCL-5, with a cutoff of 33. A mindfulness measure (FFMQ) is used for all participants at baseline to ensure it does not become a confounding variable.

TREATMENT

The mind-body therapies that will be used in this study are EMDR, MBSR and NeuroACT as these have already been implicated as feasible in this population. While these don't necessarily have to be all researched in the same study, as funding and other limitations may not allow for it, it is recommended for consistency in practice and analysis.

EMDR protocol

The standard EMDR protocol can be used, available in different languages, with certain adaptations to the procedure. These adaptations are outlined in Fischer et al., 2022, and Lievegoed et al., 2013.

MBSR protocol

The standard Dr. Jon Kabat-Zinn's protocol can be used, with adaptations for autistic populations. These adaptations are outlined in Braden et al., 2022, Lunskey et al., 2022, and Spek et al., 2013. Additionally, the procedure for a women-only virtual group is outlined in Redquest et al., 2022. After taking evidence from the scoping review into account, this author recommends group treatments with one group being only non-men. However, if there are enough participants and the preliminary interviews provide enough motivation to do so, there can also be a group for only gender-diverse individuals, i.e. not including cis men or women. This would then require changing the 'non-men' group to a women-only group.

NeuroACT protocol

The full NeuroACT protocol is available in Pahnke et al., 2023, p.1465.

TAU protocol

A full overview of the protocol for psychoeducation for autism is outlined in section 9 of the cited study, no other protocols could be found by this author as reported in the cited study as well (Beresford et al., Section 9, 2023). Adaptations for trauma focused psychoeducation and TF-CBT in this population can be drawn from Peterson et al., 2019.

MEASURES

The randomised controlled trials will report quantitative outcomes through self-reported questionnaires in order to investigate the efficacy and impact of the therapies. The use of these questionnaires also contribute to the

building of their validity and reliance in this population. Gender differences will be specifically analysed within the measures as we have argued for its structuring factor in diagnostic processes and lived experience of autism.

Feasibility Measures

Treatment feasibility and intervention satisfaction will be measured through the AD-TCS and SCS-SF.

Primary Outcomes

Primary outcomes will be PTSD symptoms, quality of life, anxiety and depression symptoms [psychological distress] as well as mindfulness scores. These will be assessed through the ADIS-C-PTSD section, QoLI, DASS-21 and FFMQ-SF.

Secondary Outcomes

Secondary outcomes will be autistic core traits, sleep problems and stress. The secondary outcomes will be assessed through the Social Responsiveness Scale and the Adult Autism Spectrum Quotient (SRS and AQ), Karolinska Sleep Questionnaire (KSQ) and the Perceived Stress Scale – 14 Items (PSS-14).

CONCLUSIONS

This thesis has sought to address the marginalisation of autistic women and gender-diverse individuals in both diagnostic practices and therapeutic interventions and other significant gaps in autism and trauma research. Through a multi-stage mixed-methods research proposal, drawing on literature reviews, expert perspectives, and a scoping review, this project has laid the foundation for future clinical trials that prioritise individual lived experience through inclusive, gender-sensitive, trauma-informed and autism-informed care. These trial methodologies are not fully-fledged protocols but frameworks for future researchers.

The findings across the expert study, literature review and scoping review reveal not only the lack of trauma-focused treatments designed for this population but also the consensus among clinicians for the need for these tailored treatments and screening methods. This builds on the research showing the unique ways in which trauma is experienced and expressed by autistic individuals, particularly women and gender-diverse people. The thematic analysis of expert responses further underscores the diversity within autistic people, and the need for trauma training and treatment models tailored to autistic people and individual cognitive processing styles. The scoping review complements this by identifying both the promise and limitations of current mind-body therapy methodologies in autism populations, highlighting a clear direction for methodologically sound future trials.

This thesis outlined mind-body therapies that may offer an effective and accessible alternative to traditional trauma treatments which often rely on verbal and cognitive processing that may be challenging for autistic individuals. The proposed study of EMDR, MBSR, and NeuroACT within a randomised controlled trial takes into account the projects research and past methodologies to build knowledge in this area. This is enriched by qualitative interviews that capture participants' lived experiences of the treatments. Such integration is not only a methodological strength but also reflects the thesis's core commitment to using mixed methods to its full advantage. While ambitious in scope, this thesis' structure was necessary to map a previously uncharted research landscape and inform the proposed studies.

However, there are additional general limitations to discuss. Firstly, the preliminary nature of the literature review and the scoping review's reliance on a limited number of studies. Most of the studies on autism featured small, male-dominated samples, while this highlighted the ongoing gaps within autism research, it also contributes to the reliance of this thesis on a select group of studies. Additionally, intellectual disability, race and socio-economic status were not within the scope of this thesis. Future research should take these factors into account. Secondly, there was only one researcher for this project which significantly impacts the depth that this project could go into. This also may introduce bias into the project as discussed in the appendix. Lastly, while the thesis attempts to incorporate the voice of autistic people and sufficient empirical and theoretical evidence, it ultimately remains a proposal. Its findings are promising but must be validated through implementation.

This thesis offers more than a research design, it aims to contribute to the foundation of ethical, inclusive, and contextually grounded inquiry of the trauma experiences of autistic women and gender-diverse individuals. By proposing interventions that are not only evidence-based but also shaped by the voices and needs of the populations they intend to help, this project aims to move this population closer to equitable and effective mental health care. The implications of this work may eventually extend beyond academic discourse, potentially contributing to changes in clinical practice and understanding of autism and trauma.

TAKEAWAYS FOR AUTISTIC INDIVIDUALS WITH PTSD

Autistic women and gender-diverse individuals experience higher rates of trauma, multiple trauma and PTSD than the general population, but they are often underdiagnosed and underserved in diagnosis and treatment.

There is high variety and difference within autistic people. This is important when deciding your preferred communication style, sensory environment, pacing, or type of therapy; which factors of treatment may be especially important for you?

Some clinicians may not be fully trained or confident in trauma therapy, keep this in mind when choosing your mental health providers. Make sure your voice is centred in your therapy, your mental health provider is there to work with you, not on you.

Many standard trauma treatments (like psychotherapy or CBT) use protocols that aim to process trauma and emotion in a way that may not be as intuitive for autistic people, potentially decreasing their effectiveness in this population. Adapted interventions (trauma-focused CBT for example) have been used with varying success, these may be effective for some autistic individuals.

Interventions that focus on the interaction between mind and body (mindfulness, yoga, EMDR etc) could be an accessible and effective treatment worth exploring. These interventions have been trialed in this population and shown to be feasible and effective.

Much more research is needed in this field, this project proposes trials that can add to the development of reliable and valid interventions for trauma in autistic people.

Future research should be centred around autistic voices; The goal is not to "fix" autism, but to create safe, respectful, and supportive treatment spaces that honour individual experience. This project also proposes interviews that assess the feasibility, effectiveness, satisfaction and experience of the proposed interventions.

APPENDIX:

POTENTIAL BIAS

Due to the nature of the research and the researcher, there may be a potential bias in the way this thesis is conducted. This author acknowledges that their autism and PTSD diagnosis may impact the process of developing this thesis. Furthermore, their personal experience with EMDR may impact the choices undertaken in this project. While this bias is acknowledged and attempts to mitigate this through peer review were taken, there may be a leading nature to this thesis that would not be present if someone without autism and/or PTSD were to write it. However, this may be a strength of the thesis considering that previous studies have called for more inclusion of autistic researchers within studies in this field and that personal experience may enrich this projects methodology.

GLOSSARY

Lived Experience	First-hand, direct experience and understanding of an individual's personal world
Traumatic Event	An event that is experienced as threatening to an individual with consequent effect on their social and environmental functioning. DSM-5 definition is the "exposure to actual or threatened death, serious injury, or sexual violence" through experience, learning or witnessing (DSM-5-TR, 2022, p. 271).
Masking/ Camouflaging	The difference in behavioural presentation of autism in a specific context, and the core characteristics associated with autism (discrepancy between internal autistic characteristics and external presentation)
Poly-victimisation	Experience of multiple forms of victimisation or violence
Interpersonal Trauma	Trauma involving interaction with other people (ex. assault)
Mind-Body Therapies	Interventions focusing on the interaction and interconnectedness between mind, body, and behaviour (ex. breathwork, meditation, yoga, mindfulness practices, ACT etc.)
PCL-5	PTSD checklist for DMS-5. 20 questions related to the experience of symptoms of PTSD outlined in the DSM-5. A score above 33 is indicative of PTSD (Reuben, 2021).

LEC-5	Life Events Checklist for DSM-5. 17 questions about the experience of traumatic events; measures exposure to trauma (Reuben, 2021).
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Appendix table 1. Glossary of terms

LITERATURE REVIEW SEARCH

Search string in Web of Science	TI=(Autism OR ASD OR “Autism Spectrum”) AND TI=(treatment OR therap* OR CBT OR EMDR OR ACT OR psychotherapy OR intervention))
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Appendix table 2. Search string for therapies/treatments for ASD population.

Search string in Web of Science	(TI=(Trauma* OR PTSD or PTSS OR post-traumatic OR adverse OR ADE) AND TI=(Autism OR ASD) AND TS=(treatment OR therap* OR CBT OR EMDR OR ACT OR psychotherapy))
Number of studies found	36 results, 5 useful articles including case studies, one EMDR study on ASD with adverse events, and reviews.

Appendix table 3. Search string for therapies/treatments for ASD population with trauma exposure.

SURVEY

Trauma screening and treatment in autistic people

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this survey. This survey is part of a larger study which aims to explore the intersection of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) in women and gender-diverse individuals, with a focus on identifying effective therapeutic approaches. Your insights as an expert are invaluable in helping to fill research gaps and improve clinical understanding. The survey should take you about 15 minutes to complete. Before beginning, please be aware that if at any point you feel uncomfortable, you may skip questions or withdraw from the survey entirely without any consequences. Your participation is completely voluntary, and all responses will be anonymized. A pseudonym will be used for any potentially identifying information, including references to specific private practices. Your responses will be securely stored and coded for analysis and the larger study will be presented in a written report and at a conference that staff and students of University College Maastricht will attend, after which they will be permanently deleted by June 10, 2025. By proceeding with this survey, you acknowledge that you have read and understood the above information and consent to participate in the study. You have the right to access all information collected from

you in this survey, on request. If you have any questions, please contact the principal investigator, Alessia Ostuni, at a.ostuni@student.maastrichtuniversity.nl.

Q1 What kind of organisation do you work for?

- Mental health centre or clinic (1)
- Private practice (2)
- Hospital (3)
- Education (4)
- Other (5) _____

Q2 What is your role in this organisation?

- Psychologist and/or social worker (1)
- Psychiatrist (2)
- Educator (3)
- Other (4) _____

Q3 How many years of experience do you have working with autistic people?

▼ Less than one year (1) ... >10 (4)

Q4 What is the highest level of school you have completed?

▼ Less than high school (1) ... Other (7)

Q5 What age group do you typically provide your service to?

▼ Under 18 (1) ... Only adults (6)

Q6 How often do you work with/ provide your service to autistic people?

- Never (1)
- Rarely (2)
- Sometimes (3)
- Often (4)
- Always (5)

Skip To: End of Survey If How often do you work with/ provide your service to autistic people? = Never

Q7 How often do you work with autistic women or gender-diverse individuals (Transgender, non-binary, intersex etc.)?

- Never (1)
- Rarely (2)
- Sometimes (3)
- Often (4)
- Always (5)
- Unsure (6)

Q8 How often do you work with autistic people with intellectual disabilities?

- Never (1)
- Rarely (2)
- Sometimes (3)
- Often (4)
- Always (5)
- Unsure (6)

Q9 What kind of issues do autistic people most commonly present to you with?

- Social skills (1)
- Internalising problems (withdrawal, fearfulness, anxiety, inhibition, somatization, sadness and/or hopelessness) (2)
- Externalising problems (defiance, destructive behaviour, and aggression) (3)
- Other (4) _____

Q10 Were you trained in trauma screening during your education and/or career?

- Yes, during my education (1)
- Yes, during my career (2)
- No (3)
- Unsure (4)

Q11 In what proportion of your autistic patients/clients/students do you inquire about trauma history?

- None (1)
- Some (2)
- Most (3)
- All (4)
- Unsure (5)

Q12 In what proportion of your autistic patients/clients/students do you inquire about the following:

	Unsure (1)	None (2)	Some (3)	Most (4)	All (5)
Physical or Emotional Neglect (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Emotional Abuse (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Physical or Sexual Abuse (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Domestic Violence (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
Parent Mental Illness (5)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q13 Do you use formal screening methods when there are suspected trauma-related symptoms in your autistic patients/clients/students? If so, which?

- Yes, (1) _____
- No (2)
- No, but I refer them to someone who does (3)

Q14 In what proportion of your autistic patients/clients/students do you:

	Unsure (1)	None (2)	Some (3)	Most (4)	All (5)
Formally screen for trauma (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Provide treatment for trauma (2)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q16 If you provide or recommend treatment, please describe the approaches you use/recommend for autistic individuals.

Q15 How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
Autistic traits impact how trauma symptoms manifest (A/D 1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Autistic women and gender-diverse people experience trauma differently (A/D 2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The tools we have to screen for trauma in autistic people are insufficient (A/D 3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is not possible to identify trauma-related symptoms in autistic people (A/D 4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of training is a barrier to identifying trauma-related symptoms in autistic people (A/D 5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is a lack of treatment options for this population (A/D 6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Traditional trauma treatments are insufficient for this population (A/D 7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q16 Do you have any comments, remarks, or something you want to say that hasn't been mentioned in the survey?

Appendix item 1. Printed Qualtrics survey for experts in the research population.

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	95% Confidence Interval Mean		Std. Deviation	Skewness	Std. Error of Skewness	Kurtosis	Std. Error of Kurtosis	Minimum	Maximum
				Upper	Lower							
A/D_1	7	0	4.429	4.923	3.934	0.535	0.374	0.794	-2.800	1.587	4.000	5.000
A/D_2	7	0	3.571	4.066	3.077	0.535	-0.374	0.794	-2.800	1.587	3.000	4.000
A/D_3	7	0	3.286	4.315	2.257	1.113	0.249	0.794	-0.944	1.587	2.000	5.000
A/D_4	7	0	1.429	2.156	0.701	0.787	1.760	0.794	2.361	1.587	1.000	3.000
A/D_5	7	0	4.000	4.755	3.245	0.816	0.000	0.794	-1.200	1.587	3.000	5.000
A/D_6	7	0	3.571	4.474	2.669	0.976	-0.277	0.794	0.042	1.587	2.000	5.000
A/D_7	7	0	2.857	3.846	1.868	1.069	-0.772	0.794	0.263	1.587	1.000	4.000

Appendix table 4. Descriptive characteristics generated through JASP for opinion questions in expert survey (incl. Skewness and kurtosis).

Category	Description
Citation	
Country	
Study Design	
Aim/Purpose	
Population Characteristics	Sample size, age range, gender distribution, living situation, formal autism diagnosis or self-identification
Trauma Type or Focus	
Intervention Type	
Intervention Details	Duration, frequency, setting, who delivered it (therapist, yoga teacher),
Adaptations for ASD	
Outcome Measures	What outcomes were measured and what instruments/tools were used (PCL-5, qualitative interviews)
Main Findings	
Feasibility/Acceptability	Reported dropout rates, participant feedback, adherence, qualitative perceptions
Consideration of Gender	Whether gender differences or specific gender-related findings are reported or discussed
Limitations	

Appendix table 5. Data Extraction Template for Scoping Review

	Citation	Country	Study Design	Aim/Purpose	Recruitment Strategy	Population Characteristics							
						Sample size	Age	Gender Distribution (type, %women /GDI)	Medication allowed	Comorbidity	PTSD diagnosis	Autism Diagnosis	Trauma Type or Focus
1 - P T S D F O C U S	Lobregt-van Buuren et al. (2019)	Netherlands	Non-randomised add-on study	Effectiveness of EMDR on trauma symptoms, distress and autistic traits	Outpatient service of mental health institutes and ASD specialist clinics [Suspected PTSD]	21	Adult (m=34)	M/F, 38.1%	Yes, no changes	Yes, except current mania or psychoses	>4 points on the Adapted Anxiety Disorders Interview Schedule-Children (ADIS-C) PTSD section	DSM-IV diagnosis by experienced clinician - any ASD	DSM-5 trauma types + Bullied at school and work, Emotional mismatch parents and child, (Secrecy) adultery mother, Adverse treatments in hospital as a child, Jarring divorce parents/ partner, Experiencing crime (racketeering, burglary)
2	Spek et al., 2013	Netherlands	RCT	MBT-AS efficiency for distress, rumination and positive affect	from the Adult Autism Centre of Eindhoven [referred as having symptoms of depression, anxiety and/or rumination]	41	Adult (m=44)	M/F, 34.1%	Yes, no changes	Yes, except genetic conditions or other neurodevelopmental disorders and institutionalisation and ID		DSM-5 diagnosis -any ASD	
3	Braden et al., 2022	USA	RCT	Effectiveness of mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) for improving health-, disability-, and autism-related QoL	Not specified	55	Adult (m=30)	M/F 38%	Unclear, no seizure medication	Yes, except substance abuse, psychoses and schizophrenia		Self-reported diagnosis and clinician screening on ADOS	
4	Kiepel et al. (2014)	Netherlands	Cohort	long-term effects of MBT-AS on psychological symptoms	from the Adult Autism Centre of Eindhoven [referred as having symptoms of depression, anxiety and/or rumination]	50	Adult	M/F 32%	Yes, no changes	Yes, except SUD, genetic conditions or other neurodevelopmental disorders and institutionalisation and ID		DSM-5 diagnosis -any ASD	
5	Pahnke et al., 2023	Sweden	RCT	Feasibility and preliminary effectiveness of an ACT group protocol (NeuroACT) adapted for autistic adults in a psychiatric outpatient setting compared with treatment as usual (TAU)	recruited at the Neuropsychiatric Unit Karolinska, Psychiatry Northwest, Stockholm City Council, Sweden	39	Adult (m=39)	M/F 46%	Yes, no changes	Yes, except SUD, genetic conditions or other neurodevelopmental disorders, suicidality, brain injury and institutionalisation and ID		Clinical Interview, Self rating questionnaires (AQ and WURS), family member interview - any ASD	

6	Lunks et al., 2022	Canada	Cohort	MBSR feasibility in terms of demand, acceptability, implementation, practicality, adaptation, and limited efficacy testing	through agencies across Canada that work with autistic people and their families. Flyers advertising the groups were also shared through social media	37	Adult (m=31)	M/F/NB 38%+5%	Not specified	Not specified		Self-reported diagnoses	
7	Redquest et al., 2022	Canada	Cohort	Preliminary evaluation of a virtual mindfulness group piloted for autistic women. Five key areas of feasibility were assessed in the current study: demand, implementation, acceptability, practicality, and limited efficacy testing.	through agencies across Canada that work with autistic people and their families.	28	Adult (m=35.9)	F only	Not specified	Not specified		Self-reported diagnoses	

Appendix table 6. Scoping Review Data Extraction for Intervention Trials (part 1)

	Intervention Details								Outcome Measures				
	Intervention Type	Frequency (Session number)	Duration (hrs/session, weeks of treatment)	Delivery/Setting	Control	Follow up	Guidance	Adaptations for ASD	Outcomes	Measurement	Main Findings	Feasibility	Limitations
IP TSD FOCUS	EMDR	3 to 8	uns., 4-8w	Individual, Clinical	Within-group TAU before intervention [pharmacotherapy, psychoeducation, supportive counselling, job coaching, support with housekeeping and so called case management]	6w (post TAU), post EMDR (4-8w), 8w FU	EMDR therapists	EMDR for children for more concrete language	PTSD, psychological distress, autistic traits	Adapted ADIS-C section PTSD, the IES-R, BSI and SRS-A	Significant reduction in all outcomes	High, 18% dropout rate	EMDR+TAU intervention, no real control, validity of the ADIS-C for adults

Intervention Details									Outcome Measures				
Intervention Type	Frequency (Session number)	Duration (hrs/session, weeks of treatment)	Delivery/Setting	Control	Follow up	Guidance	Adaptations for ASD	Outcomes	Measurement	Main Findings	Feasibility	Limitations	
2	MBT-AS	9	2.5hrs, 9w, Individual meditation 40m/day	Ind, Clinic al and home	Wait list	None	Therapists	Yes, concrete language, extended protocol, cognitive elements were omitted, full outline and weekbyweek protocol is available	Psychological distress, rumination, positive affect	SCL-90-R, RRQ, GMS-positive affect	Improved values in all outcomes	High, 0%	Self-reports, adults with average to high verbal abilities
3	MBSR	8	2hrs/w, 8w, Ind. study for 40m/d	Group, Clinic al and home	Yes, support/e ducation	4w	MBSR instructor and ASD clinician	Yes, followed Spek et al., 2013; concrete language, 2hr sessions, no metaphorical language, no required retreat	health-, disability-, and autism-related QoL,	SF-36, BREF, DAS, AS	(1) men and women with ASD do not experience equivalent HRQoL reductions, and difficulties may be dynamic across the adult lifespan, (2) psychosocial interventions broadly may only be effective for improving HRQoL in women with ASD, and (3) MBSR may have specific efficacy for improving disability-related QoL in men and women with ASD across the adult lifespan.	High, 20%	Pilot study, adults with average to high verbal abilities, waitlist should be used, QoL measures that were not specifically developed for the ASD population
4	MBT-AS	9	2.5hrs, 9w, Individual meditation 40m/day	Ind, Clinic al and home	None	9w	Therapists	Yes, concrete language, extended protocol, cognitive elements were omitted, full outline and weekbyweek protocol is available	Psychological symptoms	SCL-90-R, RRQ, GMS-positive affect	Symptoms of anxiety, depression, agoraphobia, somatization, inadequacy in thinking and acting, distrust and interpersonal sensitivity, sleeping problems, general psychological and physical well-being, and	High, 13%	Self-reports, adults with average to high verbal abilities, no control

Intervention Details									Outcome Measures				
Intervention Type	Frequency (Session number)	Duration (hrs/session, weeks of treatment)	Delivery/Setting	Control	Follow up	Guidance	Adaptations for ASD	Outcomes	Measurement	Main Findings	Feasibility	Limitations	
5	NeuroACT	14	2.5hrs, 14w, ind. homework 5/w	Group, Clinical and home	TAU + waitlist	6m	Therapists	Yes, Additional sessions	IQ, Psychiatric diagnoses, Feasibility, 1. Stress, Quality of Life, 2. Depression, Anxiety, Sleep problems, Functional Impairment, Psychological Inflexibility, Cognitive Fusion, Cognitive and Behavioural Avoidance, Autistic Core Challenges, Executive Difficulties	WAIS R, MINI, AD-TCS, 1. PSS-14, QOLI, SWLS, 2. BDI-II, BAI, KSQ, SDS, AAQ-7, CFQ, CBAS, SRS, DEX-S	rumination declined statistically significantly improved primary outcomes of perceived stress and quality of life, with moderate to large effect sizes. reduced psychological inflexibility, cognitive fusion, cognitive and behavioural avoidance, and AM were statistically significant, with moderate to large effect sizes.	High	Small sample, self-report for outcomes, sample was from an outpatient clinic, no control group effects, average IQ at least.
6	MBSR	6	1hr, 6w, ind. Homework	Group, Virtual	None	12w	Autistic MBSR practitioner, ASD clinician	Yes, autistic leadership, structure, and sensory, shorter sessions (60 min as opposed to two and a half hours), shortening the guided meditations in sessions as well as the recordings for home practice, removing the full-day silent meditation retreat, and reducing the total number of sessions, guidance by autistic advisors who had done MBSR before, participation of autistic advisors in sessions, promotion of multiple communication options (text and audio, camera on or off), as well as anonymous polling.	Feasibility, Psychological distress, mindfulness, self-compassion, intervention satisfaction	DASS-21, FFMQ-SF, SCS-SF	The course was feasible in terms of demand, acceptability, and implementation, and improvements were reported with regard to overall distress, as well as self-compassion and mindfulness.	high	self-identification, ind. Lost to follow up, not autism adapted outcomes, challenges in designing an intervention that provides the appropriate level of detail to each of the autistic participants, whose learning styles and mindfulness backgrounds vary

Intervention Details									Outcome Measures				
Intervention Type	Frequency (Session number)	Duration (hrs/session, weeks of treatment)	Delivery/Setting	Control	Follow up	Guidance	Adaptations for ASD	Outcomes	Measurement	Main Findings	Feasibility	Limitations	
7	MBSR	6	1hr, 6w, ind. Homework	Group, Virtual	None	None	Autistic MBSR practitioner, ASD clinician	Yes, autistic leadership, structure, and sensory, shorter sessions (60 min as opposed to two and a half hours), shortening the guided meditations in sessions as well as the recordings for home practice, removing the full-day silent meditation retreat, and reducing the total number of sessions, guidance by autistic advisors who had done MBSR before, participation of autistic advisors in sessions, promotion of multiple communication options (text and audio, camera on or off), as well as anonymous polling.	Feasibility, Psychological distress, mindfulness, self-compassion, intervention satisfaction	DASS-21, PHQ-9, GAD-7 FFMQ-SF, SCS-SF	Results showed that the program was feasible in terms of demand, implementation, practicality, and acceptability. While quantitative results showed there were no changes in psychological distress, self-compassion, and mindfulness from pre- to post-program, qualitative results showed some benefits.	High	

Appendix Table 7. Scoping Review Data Extraction for Intervention Trials (part 2)

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	13
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	Click here to enter text.
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	13
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	13
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web	/

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
		address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	14
Information sources*	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	14
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	14
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	14
Data charting process‡	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	14
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	14
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence§	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	14
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	14
RESULTS			
Selection of sources of evidence	14	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	15
Characteristics of sources of evidence	15	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	16
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	.
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	17
Synthesis of results	18	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	17
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	17

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
Limitations	20	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	17
Conclusions	21	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	17
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	/

Appendix Table 8. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist.

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